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Social Participation in the Italian Regions During the period 2013-2022

It decreased by 20.18%

Istat calculates the value of social participation. The variable is defined as people aged 14 years and over who have carried out at least one social participation activity in the last 12 months out of the total number of people aged 14 years and over. The activities considered are: participating in meetings or initiatives (cultural, sporting, recreational, spiritual) organized or promoted by parishes, congregations or religious or spiritual groups; participate in meetings of cultural, recreational or other associations; participate in meetings of ecological, civil rights and peace associations; participate in meetings of trade union organizations; participate in meetings of professional or trade associations; attend political party meetings; carry out free activities for a party; pay a monthly or periodic fee for a sports club/club. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2013 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of social participation in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place by value of social participation in 2022 with an amount of 33.4 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with a change equal to an amount of 30.3 units and from Veneto with an amount of 29.5 units. In the middle of the table are the Marche with an amount of 26.2 units, followed by Tuscany with an amount of 25.9 and Liguria with an amount of 25.8 units. Sicily closes the ranking with an amount of 20.5 units, followed by Puglia with an amount of 20.3 units and Calabria with an amount of 17.8 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in social participation between 2013 and 2022. Campania is in first place for the value of the percentage change in social participation between 2013 and 2022 with a change equal to an amount of -1.76% equal to a variation from an amount of 22.7 units up to 22.3 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to -4.44% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 27.00 in 2013 up to a value of 25.8 in 2022. In third place is Valle d'Aosta with a variation equal to -7.06% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 32.6 units in 2013 up to 30.3 units in 2022. In the middle of the table are Tuscany with an amount of -19.31% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 32.1 units in 2013 up to 25.9 units in 2022. Marche follows with a variation equal to -20.36% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 32.9 units in 2013 up to a value of 26.2 units in 2022. Sicily follows with a variation equal to an amount of -20.54% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 25.8 units in 2013 up to an amount of 20.5 units in 2022. Basilicata closes the ranking with a variation of -28.39% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 31.7 units in 2013 up to a value of 22.7 units in 2022. Emilia Romagna follows with a variation percentage of -29.81% corresponding from an amount of 35.9 units in 2013 up to a value of 25.2 units in 2022. Calabria follows with a variation equal to an amount of -31.27% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 25.9 units in 2013 up to a value of 17.8 units in 2022. On average, the value of social participation in the Italian regions decreased by 20.18% between 2013 and 2022, going from an amount of 31.8 units up to 25.4 units.

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Ranking of Italian macro-regions by value of social participation between 2013 and 2022. The value of social participation decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2013 and 2022. Specifically, social participation between 2013 and 2022 underwent the following variations in the Italian macro-regions: Central Italy -15.77%, Southern Italy -17.31%, Southern Italy -18.32%, North-West -18.64%, Islands -20.82%, North -23.06%, North-East with -28.02%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Three clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Lazio, Abruzzo, Piedmont, Marche, Sardinia, Umbria, Basilicata, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 2: Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Molise, Puglia.

Calculating the value of the average of the clusters results in the following ordering: C2>C1>C3. The dominant cluster is therefore Cluster 2 essentially made up of the Northern regions with a particular presence of the North-Eastern regions. This is followed by Cluster 1, made up of a very heterogeneous set of regions made up of the regions of Central Italy, Southern Italy and North-West Italy. The regions of Southern Italy close the ranking. It therefore follows that social participation tends to be closely connected with an income dimension. In fact, the regions that have the highest per capita income also have the greatest value in terms of social participation as happens in the case of the Cluster 2 regions. The value of social participation tends to decrease with the per capita income as highlighted both in the case of the Cluster 1 and Cluster regions which have much lower levels of per capita income than the Cluster 2 regions. The clustering therefore tends to suggest the presence of a positive relationship between social participation and per capita income at the regional level.

Conclusions. The value of social participation decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions between 2013 and 2022. The clustering suggests the existence of a positive relationship between the value of social participation and the value of per capita income in Italian regions between 2013 and 2022. The dominant cluster is in fact made up of the regions of the North-East to which Lombardy is added, i.e. the regions that have the highest levels of per capita income. Social participation can be considered as an indicator of the efficiency of social capital. And social capital is an element associated with high levels of per capita income. In fact, the value of social participation in the South of Italy tends to be 23.00% lower than in the regions of the North, 22.00% lower than the regions of the North-West, 24.00% lower than the regions of North-East and 20.00% compared to the Central regions. It follows that it is necessary to introduce economic policies at a regional level that can incentivize the population to increase social participation since in the growth of social participation there are opportunities for enriching social capital with growth in potential income.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Macro-Regions	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	36,0	37,4	37,2	37,2	36,2	36,9	34,3	32,9	22,5	27,7
Nord-ovest	33,8	36,5	35,7	36,0	34,2	35,4	32,6	31,5	21,3	27,5
Nord-est	38,9	38,6	39,4	38,9	38,9	38,9	36,7	34,8	24,1	28,0
Centro	31,7	32,3	33,4	34,5	31,8	33,5	30,6	30,0	20,6	26,7
Mezzogiorno	26,2	27,8	29,2	26,9	27,1	27,8	27,6	24,2	16,1	21,4
Sud	26,0	26,6	28,4	26,5	27,0	28,2	27,3	24,8	16,4	21,5
Isole	26,9	30,4	31,0	27,8	27,2	26,8	28,1	23,0	15,5	21,3

Regioni	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	31,4	38,6	35,1	33,6	32,4	32,7	32,4	29,5	20,0	28,5
Valle d'Aosta	32,6	33,7	41,3	35,8	34,4	31,3	37,4	30,8	17,9	30,3
Liguria	27,0	30,2	31,0	32,0	31,7	32,0	29,4	29,8	20,0	25,8
Lombardia	36,0	36,7	36,6	37,7	35,4	37,3	33,1	32,7	22,1	27,3
Trentino-Alto Adige	45,4	47,4	49,3	47,0	44,8	46,4	44,4	39,1	28,5	33,4
Veneto	40,6	38,5	40,1	41,0	40,2	39,8	36,8	35,5	23,8	29,5
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	38,0	39,0	38,4	37,7	37,5	36,7	34,7	32,4	22,3	27,3
Emilia-Romagna	35,9	36,5	36,6	35,0	36,6	36,9	35,2	33,6	23,7	25,2
Toscana	32,1	33,5	33,3	33,2	31,4	34,3	31,0	29,8	20,2	25,9
Umbria	30,9	31,4	36,3	36,2	34,8	35,9	31,3	30,9	23,5	25,7
Marche	32,9	34,2	37,3	37,0	32,7	34,3	31,7	28,7	19,5	26,2
Lazio	31,1	31,3	32,0	34,5	31,4	32,4	30,0	30,3	20,7	27,6
Abruzzo	32,8	32,2	30,1	33,4	31,3	32,4	31,6	28,1	19,9	26,7
Molise	26,1	30,3	28,5	28,6	29,0	27,2	26,7	27,1	14,0	21,4
Campania	22,7	23,3	25,1	23,1	25,4	26,6	25,0	23,2	14,8	22,3
Puglia	27,4	26,9	31,3	29,9	28,0	28,7	28,6	27,8	17,9	20,3
Basilicata	31,7	31,0	32,2	31,8	31,9	33,5	30,0	25,9	15,2	22,7
Calabria	25,9	29,9	29,4	22,9	25,1	28,0	27,5	20,3	16,3	17,8
Sicilia	25,8	29,0	30,0	26,6	25,4	25,1	26,7	22,5	14,9	20,5
Sardegna	30,1	34,6	34,1	31,5	32,5	32,0	32,2	24,7	17,1	23,6